

Residual Paramagnetism of Cobalt in Nitro-Ammine Cobalt(III) Complexes

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IN continuation of our earlier work on electronic spectra, magnetic susceptibility and ^{59}Co NMR of Co(III)-ammine complexes¹⁻⁶, the study of a series of nitro-ammine Co(III) complexes is undertaken.

Experimental

All the nitro-ammine Co(III) complexes were prepared according to the known methods and then purified. The complexes were analysed for cobalt, ammonia and chloride by using standard methods. The data are found to be very satisfactory.

Physical measurements were made as described previously^{3,5}.

Results and Discussion

The observed chemical shifts (σ) for the complexes under investigation are given in Table 1. The values

The results of magnetic susceptibility measurements are given in Table 1. The calculation and other details of the values are given elsewhere⁵. The d-d transition energy E_{dd} refers specifically to the lowest energy band ($^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$).

The results (Table 1) indicate that the observed χ_m values for all the complexes are smaller than $\Sigma\chi_D$ values. The difference between the two is obviously due to residual paramagnetism χ_p due to cobalt, being called second order paramagnetism. Thus second order paramagnetic susceptibility (χ_p) for all the complexes was estimated. In NMR method, shifts of ^{59}Co are also due to second order paramagnetism which arises by mixing low lying $^1A_{1g}$ and $^1T_{1g}$ states. From this study one is inclined to believe that the much contribution to the shifts is due to the residual paramagnetism while the diamagnetic contribution has minor role in affecting σ values.

A salient feature is seen from the Table 1 that the successive replacement of NH_3 molecule by NO_2^- ion in these complexes from hexamine Co(III) results, in a decrease in the σ and χ_p values. Whereas in case of aquo, carbonato, azide and oxalato ammine series of Co(III) complexes, there is an increase in these values¹⁻⁶. Thus, these data suggest that ^{59}Co nucleus is more shielded in nitro-ammine Co(III) complexes. Further σ and χ_p decrease

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, CHEMICAL SHIFT, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA FOR NITRO-AMMINE Co(III) COMPLEXES

Complex	Observed Absolute σ % Values	Calculated σ para %	$10^6 \chi_M$	$\epsilon\chi_D$	$\chi_p(\text{obs})$	$\chi_p(\text{caL.})$	E_{dd} (cm^{-1})
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_3$	-2.346	-2.342	63	181	118	194	21050
2. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NO}_2]\text{Cl}_2$	-2.281	-2.239	40	154	114	185	22030
3. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{ONO}]\text{Cl}_2$	-2.400	-2.375	32	154	122	196	20750
4. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{Cl}$ Cis	-2.245	-2.204	26	127	100	182	22370
5. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{Cl}$ Trans	-2.218	-2.169	31	127	96	179	22730
6. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ONO})_2]\text{Cl}$ Cis	-2.428	-2.502	20	147	126	207	19760
7. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{ONO})(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ Cis	-2.501	-2.514	14	144	130	208	19610
8. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ Cis	-2.368	-2.336	30	144	114	193	21100
9. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{NO}_2]\text{Cl}$ Trans	-2.348	-2.357	19	137	118	195	20920
10. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{NO}_2)_3]$	-2.177	-2.144	5	100	95	177	22990
11. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{Cl}]$	-2.249	-2.219	3	110	107	183	22220
12. $\text{Na}[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{NO}_2)_4]$	-2.152	-2.070	11	103	92	171	23810
13. $\text{Na}_2[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)_5]$	-2.140	-2.036	18	106	88	168	24210
14. $\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$	-2.285	-2.385	1	109	108	197	20660

are negative since the resonance occurs at a field lower than that for the reference $\text{K}_3[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6]$ and shifts are quite large. It is also noted that the chemical shifts show significant differences for the complexes under study, reflecting differences in chemical (magnetic) environment between these nitro-ammine complexes.

The paramagnetic contribution (σ para) to the shielding tensor which dominates the ^{59}Co chemical shifts has been calculated for the complexes using the relation of Griffith and Orgel⁷. The observed chemical shift values have been converted to the absolute values accordingly⁸.

with an increase in the number of nitrogroups in the coordination sphere of Co(III), which means that shielding increases with substitution of NO_2^- groups. The increase is in the following order :

Hexamine < Pentammine < Tetrammine (cis and trans) < Triammine < Diammine < Monoammine Co(III)

From the Table it is observed that few mixed ligand and few nitrito-ammine Co(III) complexes and $\text{Na}_6[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ behave differently from the rest. This may be due to profound changes in the bonding,

reactivity of Co(III) and mixture of nitro and nitrito in the complexes.

Thus the trends in magnetic susceptibility and chemical shift values show increasing ligand field strength as one moves down the series of complexes in Table I. This is observed directly in the relative values of E_{dd} for complexes accordingly⁷.

It is also interesting to note that the observed and calculated values in σ and χ_p are some what deviating. This may be due to some factors such as covalent bonding of ligands with Co(III), uncertainties in the values of diamagnetic susceptibilities used for evaluating terms, configurational interaction (cis and trans), the distortion in the octahedral structure of complexes of Co(III), etc. which were not considered in the theory^{9,10,11}.

The data σ , χ_p and E_{dd} also may be utilised very clearly to establish ligand field strength of ligands such as ONO^- , H_2O , NO_2 and NH_3 , to study nitrito and nitro isomers and to distinguish cis and trans isomers in these nitro-ammine Co(III) complexes (Table I.)

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Extraction of Manganese(II) with Salicylaldoxime—Synergic Effect of Pyridine*

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OXIMES (mono and di) of carbonyl compounds are extensively employed as extraction photometric reagents for many metal ions¹. A survey of literature has shown that very little work on oximes for extraction photometric determination of manganese(II) is reported. Flagg and Furman² reported that salicylaldoxime reacts with many metal ions including manganese. However no work was reported on the extraction photometry of manganese with this oxime. Gorbach *et al.*³ made casual mention about the possible extraction of manganese with salicylaldoxime with chloroform. The present authors observed that the oximate complex of manganese(II) formed in alkaline solutions is quantitatively extractable into *n*-butanol. However the yellowish brown colour of the butanolic layer was unstable and deepened with time, even though the determination of the metal ion⁴ was possible, if the measurements are completed within 30 minutes. It is found from the literature* that this phenomenon of colour change is a common occurrence due to aerial oxidation of Mn(II) and addition of pyridine was suggested to overcome this difficulty. Present authors however noticed that the colour of *n*-butanolic layer was unstable even after the addition of pyridine. In contrast to the behaviour in *n*-butanol, the metal is extracted completely into toluene in presence of pyridine. The colour was also stable for long times. There is negligible extraction into toluene in the absence of pyridine. The organic layer is colourless, if the extraction is carried out without salicylaldoxime. Extraction photometric study of Mn(II) with salicylaldoxime into toluene in presence of pyridine is therefore carried out and the results are communicated herewith.

The studies pertaining to the effect of pH on the reaction between Mn(II) and the oxime revealed that there is yellow colour formation in the range 8-10. The soluble coloured complex was extracted into toluene in presence of pyridine. The absorbance of the organic phase obtained at pH 10 measured against the solvent blank showed highest value at 420 nm in the visible range (400-700 nm). The absorbance is constant for several weeks. The aqueous phase after extraction showed zero absorbance. Chemical examination of the aqueous phase showed that a quantitative recovery is achieved when the concentration of the oxime is atleast 20 fold excess and pyridine is 5% in the organic phase.

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